

**RE.
CAP**

Reinforcing CAP

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Deliverable D5.10 provides the final report on the actions that were carried out to develop and maintain the RECAP Network of Interest (NoI), as well as on the feedback that was provided by the NoI and incorporated in the project.

The NoI promoted collaboration among stakeholders and end users, and it also provided support and exchange of ideas at the development stage of RECAP platform.

The NoI built during the project implementation, is a community of groups and individuals, who share a common interest relevant to the RECAP objectives or operate in similar fields. Members of the NoI acted both as a main dissemination pole for other stakeholders, as well as the future first customer base for the commercialization of the RECAP outcomes.

The aim of the NoI was to create a pool of stakeholders that acted as multipliers of dissemination activities and thus enabled the attraction of potential users and future customers for the RECAP platform. The main approaches used to set up the NoI were email communications, newsletters, social media, person to person meetings, partner's recommendations, events and particular multipliers.

The main accomplishments of the NoI following careful and frontloaded time-planning include the following:

- A list with contact details of 8,490 members of the NoI has been established (an additional 611 members from the previous deliverable at M23).
- Each entry of the fore mentioned list has been assigned a set of categorical variables. A statistical analysis of the data collected has been carried out.
- The target set for Month 30 has been reached as early as Month 7 (1.000 registered individual users).
- Five published newsletters were forwarded via mailing lists to potential user groups and communicated through the project website and social media.
- Social media accounts in various networks were created and kept up-to-date throughout the project implementation.
- A webinar was carried out on April 2017.
- Workshops and presentations have taken place within different events.
- Pilot workshops were successfully implemented and user group active involvement in the project was achieved.
- Increased visibility of the project in social media was succeeded
- A number of person to person meetings were carried out resulting in the engagement of more members in the NoI.
- One scientific paper addressing the academic society was published and communicated and two more are underway strengthening the project's profile through its results and thus visibility of the NoI.
- The final project meeting presenting project results was carried out in the frames of INSPIRE 2018 CONFERENCE in Antwerp, Belgium.
- A series of polls was organized encouraging the active engagement of the NoI.
- Provision of recommendations to the RECAP partners for further NoI expansion and diversification.

Following the first review meeting and respective comments from the reviewers RECAP website was enriched with new sections such as: "target groups", "sign up for updates and opportunities to get involved",

whilst other sections were updated by adding a timeline in the “pilots” section, or adding new information in “the platform” section, uploading four videos, posting new events: internal and external and “polls”.

2.INTRODUCTION

2.1 Purpose of the deliverable

This is the final deliverable (D5.10 Network of Interest report) of a series of three that aims to monitor and update the NoI development on the project. It also describes the feedback received from the NoI and statistically presents the network's results.

2.2 Structure and content

The deliverable is structured in the following chapters:

Chapter 3.	This chapter provides a description of the methodology used to approach the members of NoI. Additionally the tools used for data entry and the different types of group categories that form the NoI are defined. This chapter also includes the projected metrics and targets set in the Communication and Dissemination plan (Deliverable 5.1).
Chapter 4.	In this chapter the statistical analysis of the NoI entries is presented, followed by the description of relative results.
Chapter 5.	The discussion on the statistical outcomes of RECAP NoI is presented in this chapter.
Chapter 6.	Description of the activities performed to build the network of interest and its outcomes are outlined.
Chapter 7.	Chapter 7 presents the actions performed for GDPR compliance.
Chapter 8.	Conclusions on the NoI outcomes are presented.

3. RECAP NETWORK OF INTEREST

3.1 Definition

RECAP's Network of interest refers to a community of groups and individuals representing major stakeholders including paying agencies, agri-consultants, farmers' organisations, governmental and non-governmental organizations, private companies and academic / research institutions, collective bodies and scientific communities at a local, regional, national and European level, that share a common interest related to the RECAP project, as well as the CAP and environmental protection, remote sensing and ICT.

The concept behind building the Noi was to gather potential stakeholders/users of the platform. The Noi would in turn provide useful feedback to RECAP increasing its chances for market uptake. The main objective of the Noi establishment was to act as a main dissemination pole for other stakeholders, but also to create the first customer base for the future commercialisation of the RECAP platform.

3.2 Methodology of the Noi establishment

At the beginning of the RECAP communication activities, representatives of all the project partners acted as communication channels that ensured the identification and commitment of experts in the field related to high-level of knowledge and experience in the CAP, policy making and environmental issues. Consortium partner ETAM SA has been in charge of this process. Until Month 4, all project partners contributed in suggesting contacts for the project's Noi. Note that paying agencies provided mailing lists of their personnel that count over 800 officers Lists of registered agriconsultants and producers' associations were also used to build up the network of interest.

A greater effort was given in choosing members for the Noi from countries that have greater technological penetration specifically in RS and ICT such the UK, Netherlands, Finland, Germany, Italy and Estonia.

This process resulted in the establishment of two groups, a) the Core (user) Group which consists of stakeholders who are considered to be of particular interest for RECAP and b) the General Group which includes the rest of the contacts that may have an interest in the project. The Core Group was formed from a screening activity, with the objective to limit interested users to those who have both the interest and the potential to utilise the RECAP platform, or can be the future customers' base of RECAP or can be major multipliers of communication.

Members of the Core Group received a semi-annual newsletter depicting the project progress. They were encouraged to participate in technical/scientific discussions through the project website or social media accounts, and provided their feedback for the successful implementation of the project.

Press releases and constant updates through the project website and social media were communicated to the General group. These individuals were expected to be interested in the results of RECAP and therefore, the RECAP consortium tried to keep them up to date about the project progress encouraging them also to actively participate in project activities.

Pilot workshops organized also attempted to gather relevant feedback. Relevant data are provided in chapter 6.

The RECAP Noi encompassed individuals of all relevant roles that belong to different categories of networks, associations and organisations, of private or public status. Specifically the Noi establishment efforts were focused on identifying and engaging representatives of public administration bodies, agricultural sector, environmental NGOs, representatives of EU projects with objectives similar to the ones of RECAP, experts in

the field of CAP and environmental protection, universities and research centers active in the fields of agriculture, environment and the CAP, and experts with high-level knowledge and experience in policy making, remote sensing, information and communication technologies.

The categories of stakeholders that were selected to build the pool of stakeholders were indicatively:

- Agricultural Advisory Centers/Service Providers
- Agricultural cooperatives
- Agricultural Research Centers/Institutes
- Agronomists
- Associations of Agricultural Cooperatives
- Associations of producers or merchants of agricultural inputs
- Chambers of Agriculture
- Chambers of Agronomists
- Agricultural Consultants
- Daily/weekly newspapers/magazines
- Enterprise Associations for Crop Protection
- Environmental Management Bodies
- Europe Direct Centers
- European wide media
- Farmers Associations
- Financial newspapers
- Firms processing agricultural products
- ICT developers
- Journalists / Journalists in the fields of agriculture, environment, technology etc
- Liaison Offices
- Ministries (agriculture, environment, research etc) and Regional Authorities
- News agencies
- News portals
- Newspapers/magazines (fields: agriculture/rural development, technology, start-ups etc)
- NGOs
- Organizations promoting the environment
- Paying Agencies
- Producers Organizations
- Producers Groups
- Rural Collective Bodies
- Rural production portals
- Scientific Societies (ICT, GIS, Agronomy, Agricultural Economics, Environment etc)
- Technology Transfer & Innovation Organizations
- Unions for Conservation of Nature
- Universities and Research Centers (fields: environment, remote sensing etc)
- Young farmers associations

Additionally social media were also used as a tool for building a network of interest. Specifically the following were selected as most appropriate for setting up the RECAP NoI:

Facebook and **twitter** being the most popular social networks allowing to expand the pool of possible stakeholders.

LinkedIn being the most commonly used professional network in order to establish communication with professionals and academics of the agri-environmental sector.

Yammer communities to raise dialogue with communication specialists on European Structural Funds and instruments.

Youtube and **Slideshare** to promote videos, presentations and publications.

Technical discussions and webinars are also an important tool that directly aims at engaging crucial groups of stakeholders in the platform design and decision making process. One webinar was carried out and a series of technical discussions in the frames of person to person meetings or within various relevant events, as well as the organization of user groups project workshops.

Methodology was naturally adjusted accordingly as the project progressed. A main tool used was the constant consultation of communication archives and their results to help plan the next moves to enrich and engage the NoI. Lessons learned from project communication archives were that media that had once published information about the project would welcome feedback on progress made (i.e. fresh plaza).

The 1st review of the project also offered valuable information and recommendations to necessary actions to improve the expected results from the NoI.

The establishment, management and maintenance of the RECAP NoI were an ongoing activity that lasted throughout the duration of the project. The establishment of the RECAP NoI boosted the dissemination activities and visibility of the project but also enhanced the engagement of the RECAP target groups. Additionally it provided the project partners with the necessary knowledge in order to disseminate the project objectives on local, regional, national and European level.

3.3 RECAP network categories

In order to set the basis for the analysis of the collected contact list of individuals, the categories presented in the previous chapter were narrowed down and grouped in the following ones:

1. Paying Agencies
2. General Government and Public Administration
3. Agronomists and Consultants
4. Academia and Research
5. Producers and Associations
6. Official Bodies
7. EU & EC Agencies
8. Companies
9. Media
10. Various

 Paying Agencies: this category involves payment and control agencies that are responsible for controls on cross compliance and are actively involved in CAP implementation. Paying Agencies are the main user group being also the primary potential customers of RECAP.

 General Government and Public Administration: this network group includes Public administrations, Ministries and Departments of Agriculture of national and regional governments, other Regional and National Authorities related to the CAP and the EARDF Operational Programmes. This category includes individuals who work for public organisations and authorities that are responsible and actively involved in the CAP implementation, environmental management and monitoring, and can act as a main dissemination pole to the main (user) group.

- **Agronomists and Consultants:** including agricultural consultants, agronomists, Chambers of agronomists, public advisory and extension services and authorities that are expected to form the basis of the second user group, using RECAP data for delivering support services to farmers.
- **Academia and Research:** this category includes individuals from academia and scientists from universities, institutes and research centres that are active in agricultural and environmental research, remote sensing technology and/or policy making.
- **Producers and Associations:** including Farmers, Farmer's Unions, farmers' associations and federations, producers' organisations and Unions, Agricultural cooperatives & associations and Chambers of Agriculture. This category will additionally constitute a third class of business target, whilst farmers as individuals will constitute a fourth market segment being the end users of RECAP platform. Associations are expected to use parts of the system to support their farmers in complying with the cross compliance scheme, and farmers will be requested to use the application by their control and paying agency or their consultant.
- **Official Bodies:** this network group includes EU Citizens/ Environmental Advocacy Groups, NGOs, National and International Organizations in agriculture, accreditation bodies and other organizations and bodies that are deployed in sustainable agriculture, environmental protection and policy making.
- **EU & EC Agencies:** EU's DG AGRI, DG INDUSTRY, DG ENV, DG GROW, SCAR, JRC, ENRD, EIP-Agri, etc that develop and carry out Commission's policies strategic planning and additionally disseminate relative initiatives and resources.
- **Companies:** this category includes individuals who own or work for SMEs and other private companies that are active in e-tools development and commercialization; private companies in the agri-food sector (ICT companies specialised in the agri-food sector, especially in farm management software (FMIS, DSS)) as well as companies that draw economic activity around agriculture (applications, equipment etc) and environmental technologies.
- **Media:** including various types of communication media (webpages, tv channels, radio, newspapers etc) as well as social media.
- **Various:** experts on regulatory issues related to environmental impact of agricultural production, fertilization, ground water and air pollution, relevant European Technology Platforms, Joint Technology Initiatives and Networks of Excellence etc.

The varying profiles of the RECAP project stakeholders allowed the multiplication of Nol's impact beyond its initial target groups. In this respect, the project was designed in the way that its results could be further developed in other projects or adapted to other contexts (i.e. environmental monitoring), providing opportunities for influencing policies in a wide range of issues.

Indicative emblematic members of the Network of Interest

- All Paying Agencies
- COPA-COGECA
- Several Universities and Research Centers
- DGs AGRI and ENV

- EARSEL SCIENTIFIC NETWORK OF EUROPEAN REMOTE SENSING INSTITUTES
- EIP-AGRI Service Point
- EURAF EUROPEAN AGROFORESTRY FEDERATION
- European Association of Remote Sensing Companies
- EUROPEAN ENVIRONMENTAL BUREAU
- European Federation for Information Technology in Agriculture, Food and the Environment
- EUROPEAN FORUM FOR AGRICULTURAL AND RURAL ADVISORY SERVICES
- EUROPEAN LANDOWNERS ORGANISATION
- EUROPEAN NETWORK OF ENVIRONMENTAL PROFESSIONALS
- EUROPEAN SOCIETY FOR AGRONOMY
- EUROPEAN SOCIETY OF AGRICULTURAL ENGINEERS
- GLOBALG.A.P.
- Hundreds of producers organizations
- IFOAM EU Group
- INTERNATIONAL SOCIETY FOR PHOTOGRAMMETRY AND REMOTE SENSING
- IUCN, International Union for Conservation of Nature
- Joint Research Center
- National Farmers Union
- NEREUS, NETWORK OF EUROPEAN REGIONS USING SPACE TECHNOLOGIES
- SPIE/SPIE EUROPE INTERNATIONAL SOCIETY
- The European Conservation Agriculture Federation (ECAAF)
- The European Federation of Agricultural Consultants
- WWF

3.4 Data entry

In order to list the members of the RECAP NoI, standard spreadsheet software was used. The following column variables were created to assist effective data entry: 1) Type of Stakeholder variable describing the type of organization, 2) Organisation, that includes the name of the organization, 3) Email of each individual, 4) Country, including the country that the organisation is based in and is active, 5) Group Type, variable describing if the individual belongs to the Core Group or the General Group.

3.5 Targets and metrics

The establishment and maintenance of the NoI is a dissemination activity of the RECAP project. Therefore it had to be monitored for its progress and effectiveness towards the targets set in the RECAP Dissemination Plan. The dissemination impact indicator for the RECAP NoI was set at **1,000 registered individual stakeholders** by the end of the project.

Nonetheless given the ability to hypertrack all kinds of bodies with direct or indirect interest, the communication team practically set more ambitious target values which were updated regularly since the performance was good.

4. ANALYSIS

This chapter is dedicated to the analysis of the list of individuals and groups that constituted the RECAP Nol. By the end of this project the Nol list contains 8,490 individual entries.

4.1 Group type

From the total entries of the Nol, 4,333 belong to the Core-user Group and the rest 4,147 belong to the General Group.

Group Type	Number of Entries (10/2018)	Number of Entries (3/2018)	Number of Entries (4/2017)
Core	4,343	3,825	3,246
General	4,147	4,054	3,527
Total	8,490	7,879	6,773

4.2 Country

The variable "Country" includes the country that the organisation is based and is active. The number of entries describes the number of individuals or groups or entities registered in the RECAP Nol.

COUNTRY	NUMBER OF ENTRIES 10/2018	%	NUMBER OF ENTRIES 3/2018	%	NUMBER OF ENTRIES 4/2017	%
AUSTRIA	48	0,57%	47	0,60%	23	0.34%
BELGIUM	445	5,24%	356	4,52%	177	2.61%
BULGARIA	42	0,49%	36	0,46%	19	0.28%
CROATIA	59	0,69%	55	0,70%	35	0.52%
CYPRUS	186	2,19%	185	2,35%	163	2.41%
CZECH REPUBLIC	111	1,31%	110	1,40%	98	1.45%
DENMARK	183	2,16%	178	2,26%	156	2.30%
ESTONIA	433	5,10%	430	5,46%	407	6.01%
FINLAND	72	0,85%	69	0,88%	46	0.68%
FRANCE	242	2,85%	236	3,00%	193	2.85%
GERMANY	184	2,17%	181	2,30%	91	1.34%
GREECE	3814	44,92%	3692	46,86%	3552	52.44%
HUNGARY	58	0,68%	54	0,69%	29	0.43%
IRELAND	51	0,60%	46	0,58%	30	0.44%
ICELAND	4	0,05%	4	0,05%	1	0.01%
ISRAEL	1	0,01%	1	0,01%	1	0.01%
ITALY	212	2,50%	210	2,67%	151	2.23%
LATVIA	292	3,44%	284	3,60%	260	3.84%

COUNTRY	NUMBER OF ENTRIES 10/2018	%	NUMBER OF ENTRIES 3/2018	%	NUMBER OF ENTRIES 4/2017	%
LITHUANIA	550	6,48%	479	6,08%	455	6.72%
LUXEMBURG	23	0,27%	21	0,27%	12	0.18%
MOLDOVA	7	0,08%	5	0,06%	2	0.03%
MALTA	32	0,38%	30	0,38%	22	0.32%
NORWAY	8	0,09%	8	0,10%	1	0.01%
POLAND	81	0,95%	77	0,98%	37	0.55%
PORTUGAL	44	0,52%	40	0,51%	22	0.32%
ROMANIA	93	1,10%	92	1,17%	76	1.12%
RUSSIA	4	0,05%	3	0,04%	1	0.01%
SERBIA	177	2,08%	13	0,16%	8	0.12%
SLOVAK REPUBLIC	63	0,74%	62	0,79%	50	0.74%
SLOVENIA	52	0,61%	49	0,62%	40	0.59%
SPAIN	279	3,29%	268	3,40%	222	3.28%
SWEDEN	102	1,20%	102	1,29%	83	1.23%
SWITZERLAND	36	0,42%	34	0,43%	16	0.24%
THE NETHERLANDS	105	1,24%	100	1,27%	64	0.94%
TURKEY	2	0,02%	2	0,03%	2	0.03%
UK	392	4,62%	317	4,02%	225	3.32%
USA	3	0,04%	3	0,04%	3	0.04%
TOTAL	8,490	100,00%	7,879	100,00%	6,773	100.00%

4.3 Type of stakeholder

The variable “Type of stakeholder” describes the type of organisation to which the registered individuals belong.

TYPE OF STAKEHOLDER	NUMBER OF ENTRIES 10/2018	%	NUMBER OF ENTRIES 3/2018	%	NUMBER OF ENTRIES 4/2017	%
PAYING AGENCIES	2.276	26,81%	2.221	28.19%	2,184	32.25%
GENERAL GOVERNMENT & PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION	1.016	11,97%	995	12.63%	993	14.66%
AGRONOMISTS & CONSULTANTS	344	4,05%	136	1.73%	77	1.14%
ACADEMIA & RESEARCH	893	10,52%	890	11.30%	888	13.11%
PRODUCERS & ASSOCIATIONS	1.310	15,43%	1.055	13.39%	985	14.54%
OFFICIAL BODIES	660	7,77%	658	8.35%	480	7.09%
EU & EC AGENCIES	271	3,19%	208	2.64%	143	2.11%
COMPANIES	298	3,51%	295	3.74%	121	1.79%
MEDIA	616	7,26%	615	7.81%	611	9.02%

TYPE OF STAKEHOLDER	NUMBER OF ENTRIES 10/2018	%	NUMBER OF ENTRIES 3/2018	%	NUMBER OF ENTRIES 4/2017	%
VARIOUS	806	9,49%	806	10.23%	291	4.30%
Total	8,490	100%	7,879	100%	6,773	100%

4.4 Social media and website network analysis

The data regarding the RECAP website appeal to stakeholders were provided by Google Analytics. Relevant data from social media was provided by the built-in analytics of the corresponding platforms. Note that RECAP website managed to reach more than **10,000 unique visitors**.

	15 October 2018	March 2018	April 2017	% 10/2018-4/2017	% 3/2018-4/2017
Website					
Sessions	16,482	11,370	3,085	434%	269%
Users	10,559	6,816	1,481	613%	360%
PageViews	41,899	29,611	8,670	383%	242%
Facebook					
Total Page Likes	382	315	189	102%	67%
Page Views	1,883	1,461	172	995%	749%
Reach	25,724	21,298	2,243	1047%	850%
Post Engagements	520,757	12,184	2,055	25241%	493%
Twitter					
Followers	408	304	78	423%	290%
ReTweets	938	851	136	590%	526%
Post Likes	2,999	2,709	352	752%	670%
Link clicks	535	426	95	463%	348%
LinkedIn					
Followers	156	94	63	148%	49%
Post Likes	1,492	1,252	680	119%	151%
Yammer					
Followers	57	37	18	217%	106%
Post Likes	465	397	147	216%	170%
SlideShare					
Total views	945	921	533	77%	73%
On SlideShare	938	921	533	76%	73%
Shares	17	11	11	55%	0%
Downloads	12	12	5	140%	140%
YouTube				% 10/18-3/18	
Views	829	330	N/A ¹	151%	

	15 October 2018	March 2018	April 2017	% 10/2018-4/2017	% 3/2018-4/2017
Total View Duration	20:25:00	9:15:00	N/A	121%	
Average View Duration	0:02:01	0:01:41	N/A	20%	

ANNOUNCEMENTS ON 10,000 UNIQUE VISITORS

The screenshot shows a Facebook post from the 'RECAP H2020 Project' page. The post text reads: 'We are more than happy to announce that we've managed to reach more than 10,000 unique visitors of the RECAP website !!! #RECAP #remote_sensing #agricultural_sector #environment #CAP #new_CAP #CAP_simplification #paying_agencies #agricultural_consultants #CwRS'. Below the text is a promotional banner for the website 'www.recap-h2020.eu' featuring the RECAP logo and the text '10,000 unique visitors'. The banner also includes a small European Union flag and the text 'This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 693171'. The post shows 239 people reached and 2 shares.

RECAPH2020 Project @RECAP_H2020

Tweets **458** Following **284** Followers **409** Likes **634** Lists **3** Moments **0**

8 12

RECAPH2020 Project @RECAP_H2020 · Sep 13

We are more than happy to announce that we've managed to reach more than 10,000 unique visitors of the RECAP website !!!

#RECAP #remote_sensing #agricultural_sector #environment #CAP #new_CAP #CAP_simplification #paying_agencies #agricultural_consultants #CwRS

www.recap-h2020.eu

10,000 unique visitors

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 693171.

5 9

in Search

Home My Network Jobs Messaging Not

Your communities

Groups

- URBANFLUXES Project
- RECAPH2020 Project
- The Official Deree Alumni ...
- See all

Discover more

3 Likes

Like Comment

Ioanna Antonopoulou
Head of the Administration Dept at ETAM SA - CONSULTING SERVICES
1mo

We are more than happy to announce that we've managed to reach more than 10,000 unique visitors of the RECAP website !!!

#RECAP #remote_sensing #agricultural_sector #environment #CAP #nei ...see more

www.recap-h2020.eu

10,000 unique visitors

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 693171.

3 Likes

RECAPH2020 Project

NEW CONVERSATIONS
ALL CONVERSATIONS
FILES
SEARCH

Home
Messages
Notifications

REGIONNETWORK GROUPS +

RECAPH2020 Project

All Network 9

+ Create a group

Discover more groups

IA

Ioanna Antonopoulou – September 13 at 1:23 PM

We are more than happy to announce that we've managed to reach more than 10,000 unique visitors of the RECAP website !!!

UNLIKE
REPLY
SHARE
EDIT
...

You and EMMANOUIL TSANTAKIS like this Seen by 36

IA

5. DISCUSSION ON THE STATISTICAL OUTCOMES

This chapter presents a brief discussion on the results of the ongoing and renewed list of the Network of Interest as statistically analysed in the previous chapter. It needs to be noted that with the contribution of all members of the communication team responsible for the compilation of the first list of members of the network, it was made possible to achieve such large numbers of members. Following the frontloaded work management plan, the team has put their best effort to identify, locate and engage most of the individual entries of the list. The development of the NoI was an ongoing procedure and despite the number of members achieved from the beginning of the project, it lasted throughout the duration of the project. Additional members were added to the RECAP NoI, whilst the RECAP project recognition and dissemination activities expanded the NoI further.

Regarding the variable “Group type”, the 4,343 entries of the Core Group represented 48.85% of the NoI whereas the General Group with 4,147 entries represented the 51.15% of the network. An even distribution of the two groups has successfully been established. Note that an increase of 20.22% and 7.75% was achieved comparing to the previous reports’ results (04/2017 and 3/2018 respectively), whilst a 25.26% 11.93% increase was managed on the Core Group entries comparing to 04/2017 and 3/2018 reports .

Regarding the variable “Country”, a heterogeneous distribution of entries from 37 different countries is observed. The existence of 3,814 entries (44.92%) from Greece is attributed to the fact that four of the project partners have their headquarters there (ETAM, DRAXIS, NOA & OPEKEPE), whilst OPEKEPE being itself a paying agency has contributed in a great number of entries in the core group.

Finally, regarding the variable “Type of Stakeholder”, 2,276 (26.81%) entries were personnel of Paying Agencies, while the contacts originated from General Government & Public Administration, Academia & Research and Producers and Associations had approximately the same representation in the NoI with 11.97%, 10.52 % and 15.43% respectively. The dominance of Paying Agencies entries was both expected and targeted given that it is the main core target group of RECAP. Nonetheless comparing to 2017 Deliverables results the variation in percentages between stakeholders has been reduced (eg Paying Agencies represented 32.25% of the stakeholders and now 26.81%, Agronomist & Consultants count almost double entries reaching 136 from 77 members). This was a result of attempts that were not solely focused on collecting new entries, but on an effort to diversify them from different countries around EU and on the active engagement of members of the already established NoI.

Regarding web site and Social Media results, a significant increase has been achieved in almost all parameters. RECAP website on the 15th of October 2018 had 10,559 unique users succeeding a 613% increase from April 2017 (3,085 users). A 749% increase of total page views was achieved in Facebook, whilst followers in Twitter, LinkedIn, Yammer and SlideShare increased by 423%, 148%, 217% and 200% respectively.

6. ACTIVITIES PERFORMED TO BUILT THE NoI

The NoI was built throughout the duration of the project and activities performed to build it had been programmed from the beginning of the project. But as the project progressed, lessons learned on its course allowed new ideas and activities to be born on alternative activities that could possibly enhance and strengthen RECAP the NoI. Such activities included the following:

6.1 Newsletters

Five RECAP newsletters were prepared and sent to the initial contact list of paying agencies via a professional mass emailing solution (Mailchimp) in November 2016 (M07), March 2017 (M10), November 2017 (M19), May (M24) & October (M30) 2018. The topics addressed were:

- The concept of the project.
- A presentation of the consortium.
- The technology used in RECAP.
- The project's progress.
- RECAP Policy Session
- Updates and news on issues relative and important for the implementation of RECAP.

Any member of the NoI was able to unsubscribe from the RECAP mailing list. However, only 10 of them asked to be excluded from the list. This is an evidence of the interest of most of the members of the NoI to the RECAP project. Moreover, 87 hard bounces occurred, meaning that either the recipient email addresses do not exist or the recipient email servers have completely blocked delivery. These email addresses were fixed or deleted from the NoI member list.

6.2 Project Workshops

Additionally project workshops addressing the user group were launched. Specifically two (2) workshops were carried out in Greece, four (4) in Serbia, and two (2) in the UK, Lithuania and Spain. Through these workshops a number of users from different core groups have registered in the RECAP platform and thus enriched the NoI and acted as multipliers at the same time. More specifically from the Serbian pilot 145 organic farmers registered on the RECAP platform and 19 representatives from 6 certification bodies. The Greek pilot has involved 75 Agricultural Consultants of Greece and representatives from Basic Payment Schemes Application Centres and 45 Farmers. UK workshops managed to reach out to 39 agricultural consultants, 34 farmers and 2 university researchers. Spanish workshops contributed to the NoI with 10 farmers and the Lithuanian pilot with 71 agricultural advisors (note that more details are presented in D5.9 Project Workshops).

Workshops organized provided valuable feedback for the implementation of RECAP. Feedback from the **Greek workshop** provided valuable information and specifically the main outcomes were that it is:

- Very useful for consultants
- Rather difficult for farmers (due to the low familiarization with IT in general)
- Great facilitation for electronic record keeping
- Work diary functionality of the platform is extremely useful for Nitrogen balance calculation
- Useful for Information / Notifications for audits
- Useful for non eligible areas etc

Similarly **Serbia's workshops** have also provided important feedback especially given that workshops organized have reached out different core groups. The following results were collected per group type:

Organic Farmers

- The platform is a useful tool for simplifying the overall document management of organic subsidy scheme and certification process.
- Difficult for farmers that are not very familiar with IT in general.
- Organic Farmers that possess a farm registered as a Legal entity in Serbia, noticed that RECAP platform workflow was missing some information that are necessary for completion of their application process for organic subsidies. With the help of the RECAP development team, extra blank spaces for such information were added.
- Automatic creation of parcels by entering the cadastral number, will be very useful (farmers with more improved IT skills).

Paying Agency (Directorate for Agrarian Payments):

- Greater control over subsidy scheme and each Organic Farmer.
- Remote Sensing component as a very useful feature that could be exploited.
- More simplified documentation process.
- As a support for implementation of the CAP, they see the platform as a useful tool for future CAP implementation in Serbia.

Certification Bodies:

- Useful for the control during certification process – monitoring of certified quantities of organic crops.
- More simplified documentation process.
- Possibility for the record keeping.
- Possibility to automatically create parcel by entering cadastral parcel number as perceived to be very useful.
- Prevention of fraud (double) registration of one parcel in two or more certification bodies.

The **UK workshop** that addressed farmers and agricultural consultants reached the following findings:

- Increased visibility and communication with the PA would be welcomed

- Platform looks easy to navigate
- Entering data for large farms may be time consuming
- Would like to see a mobile version for ease of uploading documents
- Consultants are expected to use the platform on behalf of Farmers

Workshops carried out in **Spain** came mainly to the following conclusions:

- Useful to be able to self assess every cross compliance rule per parcel.
- Crop identification by remote sensing has been regarded as the main strongpoint of the platform.
- Crop monitoring through Sentinel images is of great importance.
- The greening calculator is regarded as an interesting and useful too;/
- Paying Agencies need to upload massive data on parcel claims for the platform to become operational.
- Some of the platform functions have similar features to repetitive tools already out in the market.
- Not possible to access different users simultaneously whilst each user corresponds to only one claim.

Lithuania workshops came to the following conclusions:

- The use of similar tools was helpful and useful and they would be willing to use such a tool in the future.
- Comments provided were that improvements are necessary for map site and greening calculator, there is need for an app and interrelation of reminders and e-mails/SMS.
- One third of the respondents stated that they would be willing to pay for services in the platform.

Overall results are promising for RECAP's market uptake given that all user groups testing the platform in the workshop acknowledged it as an easy to use tool that can release them of significant administrative workload. Mainly it has been stated that RECAP tool is something they would consider using on an everyday basis. Farmers identified as the most helpful functionality the receipt of helpful advice tailored on each of the cross compliance and greening rules applying to every single plot. Agricultural consultants and advisors also recognized this functionality as very helpful for farmers but also as a tool for direct communication and provision of e-advice to farmers.

6.3 Multimedia productions

Multimedia production and posting, such as photos, video and file sharing can spread the world about a product or a project and help build awareness in a very unique and powerful way. This particular type of social media has the ability to go viral quickly. The ability of these technologies to facilitate communication is extensive.

To that end the production of two videos about the project was programmed from the beginning of RECAP. These videos were posted on you tube and they played a double role in the Nol. They attracted new

members but also engaged further established members of the Noi as they improved their understanding and interest on the project.

Both promo videos (RECAP H2020 project video #1 & #2) had high numbers of views and triggered a number of users to visit the project's website.

<https://www.recap-h2020.eu/downloads/videos/>

6.4 Multipliers of communication

In addition to the target groups that the Noi was initially focused at, all possible multipliers of communication and dissemination activities were targeted as the project progressed. Multipliers refer to all the actors that can recognize the value of the project, are motivated to disseminate its benefits further and are able to amplify the messages by bringing higher visibility to the project. Such multipliers were:

- Social media

Progress in information and communication technologies has revolutionized access to information. WP leader and all partners took advantage of this possibility through social media to multiply the reach of publications about RECAP and attract interest and members to the Noi. For example via their LinkedIn accounts members of the project team (note that project team counts at least 50 members) as well as staff of project partners not participating in the project reposted all RECAP posts in their accounts. They also reposted in LinkedIn groups they are registered in that have a significant and established Noi themselves, thus succeeding in an even greater reach. Regular posts and the practice of reposting made RECAP known to an even greater community of possible users that are no possible to be counted within the Noi, but its reach is estimated to be exponential. An indicative list of LinkedIn groups where RECAP posts were re-posted includes the following:

LINKEDIN GROUPS

1. Social Innovation in Marginalised Rural Areas
2. AgriMarketing
3. e-Agriculture Community of Practice
4. INSPIRE interest group
5. "H2020 BIOTECH" BioEconomy, Agriculture, Forestry, Food, BioScience & BioTechnology
6. "H2020 SPACE Research" Space Technology, Exploration, Earth Observation, ESA & NASA
7. Agriculture
8. European Union Regional and Rural Development Participants
9. European Society for Ecological Economics
10. European Network for Rural Development - ENRD
11. International Farming System Association - Europe Group
12. Environmental Sustainability Professionals
13. AGRONOMISTS, SOIL SCIENTISTS, PLANT BREEDERS AND EXTENSION SPECIALISTS
14. Common Agricultural Policy Network
15. Agribusiness & Agronomy Professionals (UK and Europe)
16. CAP Communication Network
17. AGRI-business Network
18. Science Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of Results
19. Partner Search Horizon 2020: Food security, sustainable agriculture, forestry and bio-economy
20. European Innovation Policy
21. Nesta
22. European Community Grants, Calls and Projects
23. International Technology Transfer Professionals
24. Enterprise Europe Network
25. Innovation Management Institute
26. Science and Technology Policy Makers Worldwide
27. Economics of Innovation and Technological Change, from Theory into Practice
28. Economics of Innovation and Technological Change, from Theory into Practice
29. Science, Technology & Innovation Policy
30. Horizon 2020, Framework Programme for Research and Innovation Group

DG AGRI has created the AGRI Research list where information on EU research and innovation financed projects is available. Platform and networking activities are supported using various tools including social media. RECAP has been registered in this list and registered in the DG AGRI twitter account. Similar lists and twitter accounts have been created for H2020 and H2020 SC6 projects where RECAP has also registered. These Twitter groups of scientific community projects, respectively count 75, 180 and 25 members and have expanded the Nol reach to the academic and research stakeholders.

Some of the main H2020 projects that are registered in the aforementioned lists are presented in the following:

Indicative list of H2020 projects

1. Sufisa H2020 funded project
2. inspiration4eu H2020 initiative
3. LIAISON2020 EU_H2020 funded project
4. FLOOD-serv Project H2020 EU project
5. ThinkNature EU H2020 programme
6. Net4Society international network of National Contact Points for the Societal Challenge 6 in Horizon 2020
7. SURE-Farm H2020 funded project
8. DARWIN H2020 funded research project
9. TOMRES Project H2020 project
10. PANACEA Network Thematic Network funded by Horizon 2020 and backed up by EIP-AGRI
11. SMART GROUND Project H2020
12. APOLLO H2020
13. e-ROSA H2020
14. SMURBS project H2020
15. ACTTiVAte
16. FATIMA_H2020
17. Fertinnowa
18. SCOOPE EU Project
19. AgriLink2020
20. AgridemoF2F
21. GAIA Project
22. TRUE Project
23. AgroCycle
24. Remix Intercrops
25. IoF2020
26. Agrispin
27. SUSFANS
28. PLAID
29. GATES H2020 project
30. Caresses
31. TASIO project
32. GRIDABLE
33. Scent
34. RE4 project
35. URBANFLUXES
36. START2ACT
37. SIMRA
38. LANDMARK project
39. INNO-4-AGRIFOOD
40. Emphasis Project
41. Smart AKIS Network

The account in Yammer network although it is not a popular social media was activated and fed with news and updates given that it offered the opportunity to connect with Communication Officers of EC. Specifically it made it possible for the NoI to connect with **18 Communication Officers** involved in structural funds and programmes and all members of this network.

Overall the importance of social media networking can be reflected by the significance of the followers that RECAP social media accounts. Some of the major **European Union institutions and bodies** that are following RECAP news and post are:

1. EU Environment The official account for EU Commission Directorate-General for Environment (DG ENV)
2. EIP-AGRI Service Point The European Innovation Partnership on Agricultural Productivity & Sustainability (EIP-AGRI)
3. ENRD Contact Point The European Network for Rural Development (ENRD)
4. Research4AGRI Managing research for Agriculture & Rural Development Committee (AGRI) of European Parliament
5. Horizon 2020 Official account for EU's H2020
6. EU Research Results Official CORDIS account
7. EU Agriculture Verified account EU Agriculture & Rural Development policy

- Press releases

Press releases were launched after every project meeting but also in the frames of workshops or participation in events. All press releases were translated in the native languages of the partners' countries (Greek, Spanish, Lithuanian, and Serbian) and also in French, German, Italian and Dutch in order to succeed in their greater diffusion in the media.

- Partner's pool of stakeholders

Partners participating in RECAP have in most cases high numbers of personnel. All paying Agencies operate branches all over their country and partners have established cooperations with a number of entities. Personnel and collaborators (clients) of partners also acted as multipliers of communication. The means used to pass on the information about the project were internal communication efforts (i.e. presentations, person to person communications, internal mails) and posts on company websites, reposting of RECAP posts on partners social media accounts and signatures on company mails with invitations about the RECAP website.

6.5 Partners engagement

All partners were actively engaged in the process of building the NoI. Apart from contributing in the initial phase of building the NoI, by providing with lists of personnel and collaborators (as mentioned in the methodology chapter), tasks were periodically assigned to them in an attempt to strengthen the NoI and its engagement. Such tasks of proposed activities included:

- Draw plan of to DOs in your country
- Draw plan of to DOs in neighboring countries
- Draw a plan of to DOs in high population countries e.g. Germany, Italy, Poland, Romania, Netherlands
- Scientific papers
- Establish connections with other projects relevant to ESA and H2020, Stakeholders in your country, Stakeholders at EU level
- Recommendations on means of target groups engagement
- Engage target groups
- Invite your connections to follow RECAP LINKEDIN account
- Feedback received about the platform and project
- European media recommendations, contacts or initiatives on your own
- Science journalists recommendations, contacts or initiatives on your own
- Bloggers recommendations, contacts or initiatives on your own
- Write content in your language to post on your own social media
- Provide content in your language to re-post on RECAP social media
- Promote social media posts, polls invitations and results
- Recommend polls and indicate questions to start discussion
- Project's brochures circulation
- Appearances in press and media
- Press interviews
- Presence in non-project events

Similarly targets were periodically set with respect to the number of unique users / visits per country on the project website and social media.

6.6 Advisory board engagement

The Advisory Board is composed of Policy advisors, agricultural consultant and members of the academic & scientific society. They all are emblematic scientists and professionals whose involvement in the project has given added value to it. Additionally they have acted as multipliers of communication through their networks of associates and partners increasing the diffusion of RECAP in the countries and areas they operate.

6.7 Users engagement

Raising the interest and engaging the NoI was target that was set by the consortium in order to achieve maximum result in the future uptake of the product, given that the target metrics were successfully achieved from the very beginning of the project. Engagement of the NoI was enhanced by the conduction of a series of polls through the project's website and social media. Specifically three (3) polls took place in an attempt to maintain the communication, interaction amongst members, and interest on the NoI. Specific questions that were put under poll and analysis of relative statics are presented in the following infographics and tables.

RECAP POLL #1

RECAP poll #1

Do you believe that the average farmer of your country has the skills to use a platform requiring computer and mobile use?

- Yes
- Most Likely
- Likely
- Unlikely
- No

Launched	Responses	Countries
Nov. 2017	27	11

RECAP POLL #2

RECAP poll #2

Which of the following environmental issues do you consider to already have the most adverse effects?

- Air pollution and climate change
- Biodiversity loss
- Deforestation
- Land change and loss of landscape diversity
- Nitrate pollution
- Soil erosion and degradation
- Unsustainable use of water

Launched	Responses	Countries
Jan. 2018	61	21

RECAP POLL #3

RECAP poll #3

www.recap-h2020.eu

Do you think the Common Agricultural Policy could be simpler if satellite data, geo-tagged photos or other supporting documentation were furthermore used to reduce on-farm checks that are necessary for the EU to issue payments to farmers?

- Largely agree
- Partially agree
- Partially disagree
- Largely disagree
- Don't know

Launched	Responses	Countries
Jun. 2018	28	11

Note that through polls and social media posts interest of the NoI was raised and relative comments and chats were triggered. Some examples are presented below:

7/5/2018 @ twitter

4/5/2018 – Comments on a twitter poll

25/4/2018 - email request to provide recommendations for a better control and monitoring of the CAP

30/5/2018 - email with a question whether RECAP includes a description of the LPIS data at a European level

10/7/2018 - @LinkedIn, comment on the occasion of the RECAP video inviting to consider a distributor in Romania

8/8/2018 – @Yammer, question with respect to the result of the third poll

6.8 Participation in events

Workshops presenting the project to possible users also took place in the frames of different events, whilst presentations of RECAP have taken place in larger scale European events resulting in the large diffusion of RECAP results and enrichment of the NoI. Some of the events where RECAP was presented to organizations, researchers and public authorities related to the Common Agricultural Policy include the following:

DATE	COUNTRY	EVENT	PARTNER
6/6/2016	UK	CEREALS 2016	Strutt & Parker / UoR (University of Reading)

DATE	COUNTRY	EVENT	PARTNER
21-22/09/2016	Belgium	EU Research and Innovation in Support of the Earth Observation Workshop	NOA
10/2016:	Belgium	Learning Network Meeting Directors of Paying Agencies and Coordinating Bodies	OPEKEPE, NMA
25/11/2016	Portugal	22nd MARS Conference	DRAXIS
29/3/2017	Serbia	IoT in Serbia, HUBTEC/I4MS Workshop (Presentation topic: Agriculture 4.0: digitization of agribusiness in Serbia) / ICT in agribusiness companies / H2020 HUBTECS/I4MS	INOSSENS
21-24/9/2017	Greece	8th International Conference on Information and Communication Technologies in Agriculture, Food and Environment (HAICTA 2017) in Chania, Crete	OPEKEPE
26/9/2017	Serbia	International forum on organic production in Selenca	INOSSENS
12/10/2017	Serbia	Biofest conference: IT Organic Vision of Future Serbia	INOSSENS
24/10/2017	Belgium	Participation of RECAP in the eGov event.	DRAXIS
3/11/2017	Greece	10th annual seminar FONCIMED network	OPEKEPE
28-29/11/2017	Ireland	23rd MARS conference	NOA
17/11/2017	Belgium	Presentation of RECAP in the EC workshop: "Digitising agriculture & food value chains"	DRAXIS
12/2017	Belgium	COPA COGEGA	CREVIS
21-22/2/2018	Poland	EUFRAS International conference "Challenges for agricultural advisory after 2020"	LAAS
26/4/2018	Latvia	EIP-AGRI workshop: "Enabling farmers for the digital age: the role of AKIS".	DRAXIS
5/2018	Spain	Conferences on the Control of Direct Aids of the CAP in Sevilla	INTIA
20/9/2018	Belgium	INSPIRE Conference	DRAXIS, NOA, CREVIS
9/10/2018	Belgium	COPERNICUS Ecosystem Workshop	DRAXIS

The RECAP project will be presented at the 10th meeting of the Strategic Working Group on Agriculture Knowledge and Innovation Systems of the Standing Committee of Agricultural Research, taking place in Brussels on 30-31 of October 2018.

Note that RECAP was also discussed in PANTA RHEI conferences 2016 & 2017, which bring together representatives from all the EU member states paying agencies. In an attempt to strengthen user involvement a questionnaire was distributed to the PA directors including asking specific information on their needs and expectations from RECAP to help «tailor make» the product. Results provided with significant insights on competitive products and specific problems faced per country on CAP monitoring.

It needs to be mentioned that presentations of RECAP also took place for the benefit of possible user groups such as: the Flemish paying Agency (11/2017), OPEKEPE (3/2018), the Agrarian Enterprise of the young farmers of Navarra (12/2016, 1/2017 & 9/2017), EU Info Point – Novi Sad (11/17 & .04/2018), University of Reading (6/2017) and the Danish Paying Agency (10/2017).

The final meeting event was organized in the frames of INSPIRE conference that was held from 18 to 21 September, by the European Commission, in Antwerp, Belgium.

A presentation of RECAP took place at the parallel sessions held in the thematic GEOINT for Environmental Compliance Assurance in rural areas/agriculture where at least 40 individuals attended the presentation expanding further the Nol. The project consortium had the opportunity to share experiences and present project results to a broad audience of stakeholders. Amongst others, several representatives of EU and national public institutions as well as farmers' representatives and experts from the EO industry attended and actively participated in the open discussion of the workshop.

6.9 Person to person meetings

Finally a series of person-to-person meetings with key policy making actors and a variety of stakeholders have taken place. All actions mentioned ensured the Nol multiplied dissemination actions and created a solid base of possible users for the platform.

Some of the most important types of stakeholders reached included the following:

- European Council of Young Farmers
- CEETTAR (European Organisation of Agricultural and Rural Contractors)
- COPA-COGECA the European farmer's representative and agricultural cooperatives umbrella organisation.
- EU officials – policy makers – project officers of similar projects aiming at developing synergies.
- Waag Society - Head of Program, Smart Citizens Lab
- DG AGRI, DG GROW policy officers

7. NoI GDPR COMPLIANCE

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) - which replaces the Data Protection Act 1998, came into force on May 25 2018. Under GDPR rules any entity possessing personal data should make sure that all data has been collected under the positive consent of the Data subject (an individual who is the subject of personal data)

RECAP NoI falls into the GDPR rules as processing of personal data takes place (processing is the act of obtaining, recording, holding or using personal data), where the RECAP WP leader is both the Data controller (decides how personal data is processed and needs the consent of the data subject to do this) and the Data processor(processes data).

Given that RECAP NoI was built from the beginning of the project (before the law came into force) personal data was collected either by published data or was presented to the members of the consortium (mainly its personnel) but without its written consent of the data subject. In an attempt to comply with the regulation an initial email was sent. It was informing the NoI on the RECAP project's commitment to GDPR compliance asking the members to either update their preferences or to unsubscribe if they wish. This mail also included information on the new regulation was sent on the 25/5/2018. A second reminder mail was sent on the 19/6/2018.

Note that upon the completion of the project and as required by the regulation, all personal data will be deleted from the WP leader's files from all sources (data, back up and e-traces).

RECAP H2020 project committed to privacy

You are receiving this email as your name and contact information is currently held on RECAP Horizon 2020 project Network of Interest (NoI).

RECAP is contacting everyone whose information is held to make them aware and to ensure we comply with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) that comes into effect on the 25th May 2018.

If you are happy for us to retain your information we will continue to use it in order to send you updates on important RECAP related information.

[update your preferences](#)

[unsubscribe from list](#)

[**Privacy Policy**](#)

If you have any queries about RECAP's privacy policy update please contact info@recap-h2020.eu

About the GDPR:

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) is an essential step to strengthen citizens' fundamental rights in the digital age and facilitate business by simplifying rules for companies in the digital single market. The regulation came into force on 24 May 2016 and will apply from 25 May 2018. Under the GDPR you have the right to know what personal data we store, you may ask us to correct or even delete them at any time. Please note that RECAP will never pass your information to third parties.

Response on neither mail was satisfactory. Only 4.55% responded both positively and negatively. Results are analytically presented in the following table.

RECIPIENTS	Subscribed	Unsubscribed
4.569	39	169

Such a low response rate may be justified given the extensive mailing that was sent out by all entities subjected to GDPR rules during that period as the 26th of May was the deadline set for compliance to the Regulation.

Nonetheless given that all mail communications as initially planned were concluded with the 4th newsletter that was mailed on the fourth of May 2018 and the fact that data are only kept for the period of the project lack of response did not affect the project results.

8. CONCLUSIONS

The NoI was built in order to promote the exchange of ideas at the development stage of the RECAP platform and to increase its chances for market uptake. Frontloaded actions that took place from the beginning of the project resulted in succeeding the project target of 1.000 members by as soon as M4. Nonetheless efforts to enrich diversify and engage the NoI in the project kept on throughout the project, whilst different methodological approaches were followed in order to achieve at times required results.

All partners greatly contributed to this attempt either by acting as multipliers, or by contributing in the attraction of new members in the network.

Activities performed were:

- Publication of five (5) Newsletters.
- Regular posts on Social media and site of the project with news, press releases, polls etc.
- Constant presence of the consortium in large scale relevant events.
- Pilot workshops.
- Person to person meetings
- Use of communication multipliers
- Webinar organization
- Production of two promo videos

The NoI managed to attract over 8,000 members, over 4,000 of which belong in the core group. Over 1,000 unique users visited the project's website and social media attracted over 1,000 followers. Additionally RECAP was communicated to an even larger community of stakeholders through the active engagement of partners in relevant events, person to person meetings and reaching out relative communities. The results of the NoI are yet more encouraging given the degree of engagement of the network's members throughout the duration of the project, providing the consortium with feedback, questions and comments.

In conclusion, by the end of RECAP project Month 30, the NoI has been successfully established, largely overcoming the target set at the beginning of the project.